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Report from the Rev. H. H. Baber, Keeper of the Department of Printed Books, 26th April 1834, in Papers relating to the alphabetical catalogue, London, [ed.] Private and confidential. London, George Woodfall and Son, 1847, p. 41-48.

No. 3.

REPORT *from the* REV. H. H. BABER, *Keeper of the Department of Printed Books.*
26th April, 1834.

MR. BABER having been desired by an order of the Trustees, made at a Committee, April 12th, 1834, "To report to the Sub-Committee, appointed at the last special meeting, the general principles upon which he proposes to form the new alphabetical Catalogue of the whole Library; what progress has been made towards such a Catalogue; how far the Catalogues, both printed and manuscript, can be rendered available for this purpose; and how far they will require alteration, and what number of volumes and titles, so nearly as he can ascertain, are at present wholly undescribed; further to report, what time it would take, with the present establishment at his disposal, to complete the manuscript of such a Catalogue, and what further time would be occupied in printing it; and lastly, to lay before the Committee a statement of the manner in which the several officers and other persons of his department are severally employed, and of the special duties assigned to each;" he respectfully submits to the consideration of the Trustees the following answers to their inquiries.

The general principles upon which Mr. Baber proposes to form a new alphabetical Catalogue.

In the compilation of a Catalogue of this description, the whole series of the titles of the books in the library should be, in the first place, arranged alphabetically according to the surnames of their several authors, as far as their works justified such an appropriation. The author's surname to be followed by his Christian name, included in brackets; afterwards by a specification, in italics, of his rank in society, in cases in which he enjoyed any eminent honorary distinction; then should follow the contents of the title, expressed in as few words (and those of the author) as would with perspicuity exhibit all which the author meant to convey in that description of his book. The title, thus described, to be followed by the number of volumes or parts, if more than one; the specification of the size, whether folio, quarto, &c.; the place and the time when it was printed; and in some instances the printer's name, after the place at which the work was printed, should be inserted when the book was in peculiar estimation, as being the production of the press of some of the earliest or otherwise distinguished typographers, as Fust and Schæffer, Caxton, the Aldi, &c., &c. In instances in which the book was printed upon vellum, or in Gothic letters, or had manuscript notes, these particulars should be specified at the end of each title.

That, in the works which were the production of the same author, the surname should be prefixed to that title only which took precedence in the enumeration of each author's works as far as they were recorded in the Museum Catalogue; and that, in all subsequent titles arranged under the same name, a short line be substituted for the same to save a repetition which would not only be needless, but perhaps dis-

tracting; that, in the order of the publications assigned to the same author, his collected works in their editions, chronologically arranged, together with their editor's name, should take the lead in this assemblage of titles, and then should follow the translations in the order of their dates, together with the name of the translator; that, when the publication consisted of two or more works of the same author, they should follow next, and that then should succeed the single works in the order which circumstances may render it most expedient to adopt. The same rule should be observed with respect to the editions and translations of the separate, as laid down for the collected works. That, in the instance of the anonymous publications, there should be prefixed to the title, for want of the surname of the author, some such principal word selected from the author's title, as would most immediately direct the student to that place in the Catalogue in which a production so published would be most likely to be entered, and that the name of the author, included in brackets, should be specified at the end of the title, should it be certainly known to or be reasonably conjectured by the librarian. That, in the case of pseudonymous publications, the book be arranged under its author's feigned name, and that his real name, if discovered, be inserted within brackets at the conclusion of the title.

In the long series of printed works, which embrace the collected productions of various authors upon particular subjects, and in which numerous most valuable treatises are contained, some of them existing only in their printed form in such collections, and others, though they may have been previously or subsequently printed, not having as yet found a place in the Museum Library, it would be highly advantageous to the student that the titles of such collected productions should be in some way specified; and the readiest way to do this would be to insert, in as concise a manner as possible, a syllabus of all such various treatises, after the general title of the work in which they are respectively contained.

As in the plan now proposed the productions of very many writers, such as commentators, translators, &c., &c., will be entered in the alphabetical series under the name of the author whose works they may have commented upon, or translated, &c., it will hence be requisite that a cross-reference from the commentator, &c., &c.'s name, be made to that of the original author under which such productions may be in the alphabetical series arranged. It would be desirable also, in the instances in which an author varies his name, either in the orthography or by sometimes using it in the title-page of his work in his vernacular tongue, and sometimes in Latin or some other language, to select one of these names for the heading or leading word under which all his works should be assembled, and then make a cross-reference from each variety used to the name under which his publication might happen to be catalogued. The same rule should be observed with respect to titles of rank, by giving a reference from the titular to the family name, under which a noble author's works would be entered; and also in the case of anonymous and pseudonymous writers, and the collected works of various authors, a cross-reference should be made from the author's name, when discovered, to the entry under which, in the proposed Catalogue, his production would be found. The adoption of the plan of cross-references, to its greatest possible extent, would materially facilitate research; more particu-

larly so if there were specified with all practical brevity in such reference so much of the title of the publication wanted as would identify it immediately.

What progress has been made towards such a Catalogue; how far the Catalogues, both printed and manuscript, can be rendered available for this purpose, and how far they will require alteration.

In the construction of a Catalogue which it is intended should embrace the entire number of the printed works in the Museum (yielding at least 300,000 titles), the aggregate contents of three considerable libraries, viz. the old collection in the Museum; that of his late Majesty King George III.; and that of Sir Joseph Banks; each having a Catalogue of its own; the titles of these respective Catalogues will have to be incorporated into one alphabetical series: and as these Catalogues have been formed by Librarians of distinct establishments, who, in their respective works, have been guided by different principles of construction, and have acted upon special views of their own, it would be impossible to blend them together without a revision of the whole mass of titles which form the Catalogue of the whole Library in its present state. In the process of this examination, it would probably be found that about two-thirds, perhaps three-fourths, of these titles might, with comparatively little trouble, be rendered available for the purpose of a Catalogue upon the plan above proposed; but, till the whole series of titles were more or less strictly scrutinized, it could not be ascertained which would be the titles it might be necessary to arrange in a place in the new Catalogue very different from that they may now occupy in the alphabetical series of each of the three Catalogues above mentioned; and it would be equally impossible to state how far, previously to examination, the remaining third or fourth portion, as the case may be, would require alteration. But when it is considered that the transcribed titles of the whole Library amount, as above stated, to 300,000, and that this great mass has been the production of Librarians of different establishments, and consequently not acting in concert with each other; of persons too who, notwithstanding all their varied learning and ability, have been, in frequent instances, totally ignorant of, or imperfectly acquainted with, very many of the numerous languages in which the books that have passed through their hands have been written; and that they have not all been equally careful and exact in the accomplishment of that which they were more or less competent to have done; and that some again have described their titles with an unsatisfactory brevity, and others with a minute exactness and unnecessary redundancy;—the varieties in the mode of describing a title, together with the amount of errors in language, &c., must obviously be so great as to render revision and correction indispensably necessary, if it should be determined upon to print a new Catalogue of the whole of the Library of Printed Books.

What number of volumes and titles, as nearly as Mr. Baber can ascertain, are at present wholly undescribed.

The estimated number of titles at present undescribed is about 30,000, being

those almost exclusively of the Tracts purchased of Mr. Croker, relating to the history of the French Revolution, in the course of being catalogued by Mr. Panizzi.

What time it would take, with the present establishment at Mr. Baber's disposal, to complete the manuscript of such a Catalogue.

From the details which will subsequently, in their required order, be given to the Trustees, in reply to the question respecting the manner in which the officers and various persons employed in the Library are employed, it will, it is hoped, be obvious to the Committee that, with no other aid than that derived from the persons at present employed in the Printed Book Department, no commencement at present can be made in the formation of a new alphabetical Catalogue, embracing the whole of the titles of the books now to be found in the Library, without a stoppage to, or at least a suspension of, many of the works now in hand, one of the evil consequences of which would be, that arrears of business to an overwhelming extent would accrue. If the Trustees think that it might be possible to begin the proposed Catalogue without altogether stopping or suspending the works in progress, by allowing them to proceed at a slower rate, and thus wish to know within what time such a work might be accomplished, Mr. Baber must in truth confess that he would only eventually be disappointing the Trustees if he ventured to name any period which it would take to bring to a conclusion a Catalogue proceeded upon under these circumstances, and without any other aid than what the present establishment would supply. Should the Trustees deem it expedient that a new alphabetical Catalogue, upon the plan above specified, should be begun without delay, and executed in the shortest time possible that the work, to be accurately and in every respect creditably performed, would admit of, it could only be done by appointing a competent officer of the Printed Book Department, to be exclusively occupied upon this work, aided by three sufficiently qualified assistants, one of whom should be well versed in the German and other northern languages; and by further placing at their disposal the whole series of the titles, as at present transcribed, whether classed or unclassed, it being the duty of the assistants to compare the transcribed titles with their original, in each printed book, and to make therein all necessary alterations; and it being further the duty of the officer appointed to this special business to superintend and to be responsible for the proper execution of the whole work, revising and correcting, where necessary, the titles, as fast as they passed from the assistants into his own hands, and finally arranging them according to the plan proposed for the formation of a new alphabetical Catalogue. In this state, the titles on slips might be sent to press as soon as the whole series, but not before, had been corrected and finally arranged, without incurring the expense of a transcribed copy, for the purpose, and the slips when returned by the printer might be replaced, with little trouble, in that systematic order in which they are to a considerable extent at present arranged.

Mr. Panizzi's age, activity of mind, and various literary acquirements, eminently qualify him as the superintending officer of this work; which employment he would cheerfully accept, and engage to accomplish in five or six years from its commencement, provided, that he should have the assistance of three well-

educated young men, such as the gentlemen employed upon the Catalogues under Mr. Forshall's superintendence, in the Manuscript Department. If this extensive and desirable work were thus taken in hand, Mr. Baber feels confident that it would be performed creditably to the parties engaged upon it, and hence to the satisfaction of the Trustees, eminently useful to the public, and worthy to rank with the most justly celebrated productions of its kind.

What further time would be occupied in printing it.

Mr. Woodfall, the printer, informs Mr. Baber that, supposing that the Catalogue should extend (as it is calculated it would) to eighteen volumes octavo, containing forty sheets each, it might be accomplished in one year, provided that the copy were ready for the compositor, and that a quick return of proofs could be promised. To supply the printer with copy to any extent which he might require would, when the revision of the Catalogue was completed and the titles alphabetically arranged, be very practicable; but Mr. Baber very much doubts whether any printer could carry through the press fourteen octavo sheets per week, or eighteen volumes of forty sheets in a year, of Catalogue-work, which, on account of the extra care and time such works require, are always charged for at a higher rate than printers' work in general; and he is confident that a return of proofs, sufficiently quick to keep the press going at the rate above mentioned, could not be made, if they were to be revised with all becoming care. If the Catalogue should be three years in going through the press, it would have proceeded with as much dispatch as it ought, consistently with its being performed correctly and creditably.

The manner in which the several officers and other persons of the Printed Book Department are severally employed, and of the special duties assigned to them.

The officers employed in the department of Printed Books are, Mr. Baber, Mr. Cary, Mr. Panizzi, Mr. Carlisle, Mr. Armstrong, Mr. Glover. The three first are the regular officers of the establishment; the three last are attached to it for the present, as having been librarians to his late Majesty King George the Third.

Mr. Baber gives five days in every week to the service of the Museum; upon him devolves, as Keeper of the Printed Books, the general superintendence of the department committed to his care; and he assigns to the officers and other persons connected with the library their respective duties and employments, as circumstances may require; he attends sales, and resorts to booksellers' shops to inspect and purchase such books as are immediately wanted, or as it may be desirable, when opportunity offers, to secure for the Museum; he arranges on their appropriate shelves all the books acquired, whether by purchase, by donation, or by the privilege of the Copyright Act; he makes occasionally such changes in the locality of the books already arranged, as may best economise the little space at present remaining for the reception of the perpetually increasing stores of the library; he classes the numerous tracts received in the course of every year, that they may be bound in volumes according to their subjects; he supplies the bookbinder with the various work wanted to be done for the library, and in his turn as directing officer

of the day, which is every Friday, he visits every portion of the Museum open to the public, to see whether the warders are at their respective posts, and that the visitors are observant of all due order and decency.

Mr. Cary gives five days in every week to the service of the Museum ; during which he writes out on slips of paper (in order to their being entered in the general Catalogue) the titles of all books, pamphlets, and maps, that are added to the library, as soon after they come into his hands as possible, and as much at length as seems to him to be necessary, marking on each in what way it is obtained, whether by Copyright Act, by purchase, or by gift, and in what year. With respect to foreign periodical works and other foreign books published in parts, besides thus writing out their titles, he keeps a register of them as long as they are in progress, entering the names of the booksellers from whom they are bought, and noting any mistakes or omissions which he discovers on their part ; for which purpose he finds it requisite to refer to foreign journals, &c. containing notices and advertisements of such books ; he supplies the binder with the lettering of all the books that are bound.

Mr. Panizzi gives six days in each week to the service of the Museum. The occupation allotted to him is, as it has been for some time past, the cataloguing the tracts purchased of Mr. Croker relating to the history of the French Revolution, and calculated to yield near 50,000 titles, which, on account of their peculiarities, require more consideration and reading to catalogue intelligibly than is the case with the titles of books in general. This collection may continue to give employment to Mr. Panizzi for some time to come ere it is completed.

Such are, at present, the specific duties of the above-mentioned three officers ; but besides these they have, in common with each other, various other occupations, which make considerable demands upon their time ; such as perpetually perusing catalogues of books for sale, in order to note such as it may be desirable to purchase ; examining whether books so marked, or whether others offered for purchase are not duplicates ; preparing for the printer, and correcting the sheets during their progress through the press, of the annual list of additions made to the library ; in occasionally attending upon visitors in the library or through the whole Museum ; in facilitating the researches of readers, and in a variety of correspondence connected with the business of the establishment.

Mr. Carlisle gives two days in each week to the service of the Museum. He is at present employed in cataloguing a collection of French tracts, embracing some thousand articles relating to the times and history of Cardinal Mazarin. When he terminates this work, he will be engaged upon other business connected with the Royal Library. Mr. Armstrong gives three days in each week to the service of the Museum.

The work assigned to him is entering for general use, in the margin of a printed copy of the Geographical Catalogue of the Royal Library, and opposite to the titles of the views, plans, maps, &c. described in that Catalogue, the references to the cases and tables in which these prints are contained. It will be two years before this work will be completed.

Mr. Glover gives five days in each week to the service of the Museum. Though attached to the Royal Library, he performs no duties connected therewith ; he is exclusively engaged in superintending the business arising out of the provisions

of the Copyright Act, viz., in examining the contents of the monthly parcels of books received under this Act from Stationers' Hall; in keeping, as far as is practicable, a register of the several publications constantly issuing from the press in the United Kingdom; and procuring the delivery of such books as have not been previously entered at Stationers' Hall, and in taking charge of all the periodical publications and works in progress till a volume of each is completed, then delivering it to the bookbinder to be bound before it is transferred permanently to the general collection of books.

The persons employed in the Museum, whose appointments are temporary, are Mr. Horne, Mr. Yeates, Mr. Coke.

Mr. Horne gives six days in the week exclusively to the formation of the classed Catalogue.

Mr. Yeates serves in the Library six days in the week, compiling the hand Catalogue.

Mr. Coke is employed upon transcribing titles into a third copy of an interleaved Catalogue of the Printed Books.

Mr. Grabham gives six days in each week to the service of the library. Mr. Grabham, as clerk, is generally occupied in transcribing and re-arranging the contents of those pages in the interleaved Catalogues of the Printed Books which had got into a disordered state, in consequence of their being over-crowded with titles. He is occasionally employed on the first revision of the proof-sheets of the printed list of annual additions made to the library.

Mr. Cowtan serves in the library six days in each week. He is engaged in collecting from the bookseller the works not entered at Stationers' Hall, and in making out lists of books so obtained, with their prices affixed to them, and in assisting Mr. Glover in keeping his various registers.

The attendants attached to the library are,

J. Bygrave, sen., who serves five days in each week, during which he is for the most part occupied in searching for books required by the readers, and at intervals of leisure entering titles into the interleaved Catalogue in use in the library.

C. W. Kellet gives six days in the week to the service of the library; it is his duty to enter titles into both the interleaved Catalogues; he is, however, frequently called away from that employment to assist the attendants when there is an excessive demand of books for the readers.

W. Turner, sen., Joseph Phillips, D. Buckland, H. Adams, J. Bygrave, jun., J. Turner, jun., all serve six days in every week. The two first have the special duty assigned to them of verifying the return of the books sent from the old library into the reading-room; of sorting them according to their references, that they may be replaced with the greatest possible despatch, and, when not so occupied, in providing books for the reading-room. The four other attendants are also engaged in attending to the wants of the readers, in looking out books wanted by Mr. Horne for the classed Catalogue, or by the officers in their respective departments, and in acting under the directions of the officers of the library, as each has frequent need of their manual assistance in a great variety of ways.

J. Birchell serves six days in the week, in the lobby between the library and the reading-rooms, receiving sticks and umbrellas, and seeing that no improper person obtains admission into either of the above-mentioned places. When unoccupied by this duty, he assists in cleaning the books, &c. &c.

H. Carston is engaged to give six days in the week to the service of the Museum, for nearly half of which time he is employed as a warder in the department of antiquities; the remainder of his time is given to the library, where he is engaged in cleaning the books.

The attendants attached to the King's Library, and all of whom serve six days in the week, are,

J. Williams, employed in supplying the readers with books, ascertaining that the same are returned to the library when done with, and then replacing them upon their proper shelves. During three days in the week his time is principally engaged in attending upon Mr. Armstrong, during the time he is employed in inserting the references to the prints, maps, &c., in the Geographical Catalogue.

W. Leach is similarly engaged. He is further occupied in cleaning the books in the Royal Library.

J. Griffiths serves every day the Museum is open to the public, as a warder in the department of antiquities; the remainder of his time is taken up in cleaning books and sweeping the Royal Library.

In addition to these employments, many of the attendants are, as occasion requires, called upon to act as warders in various parts of the Museum on public days, when any regular warder is absent from illness or any other cause; they are also not unfrequently engaged in fetching and carrying parcels of books, conveying letters and messages, and in the performance, under the direction of the officers, of a great variety of labour which is perpetually required in the order and management of a library which is already of vast extent, and is daily increasing in its magnitude, and in the number of readers who have occasion to consult its literary stores.

No. 4.

EXTRACT *from the MINUTES of a SPECIAL COMMITTEE, 30 April, 1834.*

THE minutes of the last Special Committee were read.

A report was read from Sir Henry Ellis, as to the method of proceeding when the last Catalogue of the Printed Books was printed, and the time occupied in completing it.

Mr. Baber was called in, and stated that in his opinion a classed Catalogue of the whole library, if completed, would not be extensively useful nor frequently consulted; that the titles formed for an alphabetical Catalogue might, after this was printed, be made available for a classed Catalogue without any other alteration than that of arrangement; that it would be inexpedient to print any portion of the new alphabetical Catalogue before the whole of it was complete in manuscript; that, if Mr. Home's labours on the classed Catalogue were suspended, his services might be